

Exercice : traduction d'un fichier BiBTeX

On donne ci-dessous l'extrait d'un fichier BiBTeX, un système permettant de répertorier des références bibliographiques.

```
@inproceedings{inproceedings,  
  
author = {Fall, Ibrahima and Bendraou, Reda and Gervais,  
Marie-Pierre and Blanc, Xavier},  
  
year = {2013},  
  
month = {06},  
  
pages = {209-217},  
  
title = {Towards a Full Specification and Use of Overlap  
Relationships between Work Products in MDE Software  
Processes},  
  
isbn = {978-1-4799-0405-1},  
  
journal = {Proceedings of the Workshop on Enabling  
Technologies: Infrastructure for Collaborative Enterprises,  
WETICE},  
  
doi = {10.1109/WETICE.2013.76}  
  
abstract = {In this paper we address the problem of modelling  
and using overlap relationships between process workproducts.  
In fact, in the current MDE context, the nature of software  
processes has drastically changed; they involve workproducts  
which are essentially large-sized models with lots of  
relationships of different kinds. Particularly, we have  
focused on the overlap relationship which consists in sharing  
model elements between process workproducts. First, we show  
that if such relationship is completely specified during  
process modelling, then process engines are able to use it to  
ensure a more optimized workproducts management which is not  
supported by current process management approaches. Then we
```

present our software process modelling and execution approach and describe the prototype of PSEE we have developed to show its feasibility.}

```
@book{Sommerville10,
```

```
abstract = {The book presents a broad perspective on software systems engineering, concentrating on widely used techniques for developing large-scale systems. Building on the widely acclaimed strengths of the 8th edition, the 9th edition updates readers with the latest developments in the field while remaining the most current Software Engineering text in the market with quality trusted coverage and practical case studies. This text is structured into 6 parts: Introduction; Requirements Engineering; Design; Software Development; Verification and Validation; Management. An up-to-date reference for software engineers.},
```

```
author = {Sommerville, Ian},
```

```
edition={9}
```

```
isbn = {978-0-13-703515-1},
```

```
publisher = {Addison-Wesley},
```

```
title = {Software Engineering},
```

```
year = {2010}
```

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}
```

Ces 2 entrées correspondent à un article paru dans une conférence et un livre. Donner une traduction possible de ces données sous la forme d'un fichier XML. Visualiser l'arbre qui correspond au document XML à l'aide d'un navigateur (remarquer les +/-).